

2024 Bioinformatics Jobs

Trends, Top Locations, and In-Demand Skills

MEET OUR TEAM

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Foreword

Dear Reader,

Biotech and pharma industries have witnessed tremendous growth over the past decade, driven largely by advancements in computational biology and bioinformatics. This transformation has not only influenced research and development but has also significantly reshaped the job market, particularly in the biopharma sector. At HackBio, we undertook a comprehensive exploration of the current job trends within the bioinformatics domain to better understand how professionals can adapt and thrive in this rapidly evolving field.

For this mini-research project, we analyzed job postings from LinkedIn, focusing on positions in the bioinformatics sector within the biopharma industry. Our analysis deliberately excluded academic opportunities, as we aimed to spotlight the dynamics within corporate and industrial settings. The data we gathered highlighted several fascinating trends that are shaping the future of bioinformatics employment.

One of the most notable findings was the surge in demand for candidates skilled in **R programming**, **artificial intelligence (AI)**, and **cloud computing**. As companies increasingly leverage big data and machine learning to accelerate drug discovery and personalized medicine, these competencies have become essential for modern bioinformatics roles. Candidates with a strong command of these technologies are highly sought after, underscoring the need for bioinformaticians to continuously upskill in these areas.

Additionally, our analysis revealed a strong preference for **PhD-level candidates**. While master's degrees remain valuable, many bioinformatics roles within biopharma emphasize the advanced expertise that a PhD offers. The complexity of data analysis, combined with the depth of knowledge required for translating biological data into actionable insights, has made advanced academic qualifications a near-requirement for many positions.

Geographically, the **United States** continues to dominate as the epicenter for bioinformatics careers within biopharma. The data indicates not only a larger volume of job postings in the US but also higher average salaries compared to other regions. We also think that the scarcity of comparable amounts of data from non-US locations further suggests that the US remains a key hub for innovation and employment in this field.

This study sheds light on the emerging trends in bioinformatics employment and emphasizes the critical skills and qualifications needed for professionals to remain competitive in the biopharma sector. We hope this report serves as a valuable resource for both job seekers and organizations looking to stay ahead in this fast-paced industry.

Enjoy!
Adewale Ogunleye
Founder, HackBio

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Executive summary

The **2024 Bioinformatics Job Market** is experiencing significant growth, driven by advancements in technology and increasing demand for data-driven solutions in healthcare, research, and industry. This report provides a comprehensive overview of key trends, top locations, and in-demand skills for bioinformatics professionals.

Key findings include:

- **Global Job Market:** The United States leads in job postings, followed by the United Kingdom and Germany. However, Canada and France have the highest applicant-to-job ratios, indicating intense competition.
- **Top Locations:** San Diego County, California, emerge as hotspot for bioinformatics careers.
- **Industry Demand:** Biotechnology research and higher education sectors exhibit the highest demand for bioinformatics professionals.
- **Skills:** Advanced analytical tools R, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and cloud platforms (GCP) are in high demand.
- **Qualifications:** Advanced degrees (Master's, Doctorate) are strongly preferred, but entry-level opportunities exist for Bachelor's degree holders.
- **Employers:** Varsity Tutors leads in job postings, followed by myGwork, University of Pennsylvania, and BioSpace.

This report offers valuable insights for job seekers, employers, and policymakers to navigate the evolving bioinformatics landscape.

How to read this report

This report is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the bioinformatics job market. It is divided into five main sections:

- 1. Global Market Insights:** This section explores key trends, job density by city, and salary competitiveness.
- 2. Industry and Sector Analysis:** This section analyzes the distribution of bioinformatics jobs across industries and recruitment trends.
- 3. Job Characteristics and Skills:** This section examines popular job titles, skill demand, and seniority levels.
- 4. Qualifications and Employers:** This section discusses common degrees, educational backgrounds, and top employers.
- 5. Appendix:** This section includes a glossary, methodology, and endnotes.

Readers can use this structure to navigate the report effectively and find the information most relevant to their needs.

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Global Market Insights

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When you think about it, caring for patients is 99 percent information and 1 percent intervention, so it's clear that with or without genomics, the paradigm is shifting. Bioinformatics brings a cutting edge capacity to healthcare.

Christopher G. Chute
Bloomberg Distinguished Professor at Johns Hopkins University, physician-scientist and biomedical informatician

2.1 Overview of Key Trends

2.1.1 Navigating the Competitive Bioinformatics Job Market

Key Insights:

- **Canada:** Leading with **78.14 applicants per job**, Canada is the most competitive market, indicating a high demand for bioinformatics professionals.
- **United States of America:** Close behind, the USA has **72.95 applicants per position**, reflecting a thriving industry.
- **United Kingdom:** With **70.62 candidates per job**, the UK showcases strong competition in the bioinformatics sector.
- **Germany:** Germany's market is notable with **69.16 applicants per job**, suggesting a healthy ecosystem for careers in this field.
- **France:** Averaging **64.92 applicants per job**, France remains competitive, though slightly behind Germany.
- **Japan:** Japan's market, with **64.86 applicants per job**, requires distinct expertise to stand out.
- **Netherlands:** The Netherlands has **63.88 applicants per job**, indicating a highly competitive environment.

Conclusion:

This data-driven analysis highlights the intense competition for bioinformatics talent across these nations. Job seekers and employers must strategically position themselves to capitalize on opportunities within this dynamic field.

2.1.2 Global Hotspots for Bioinformatics Careers

Key Insights:

- **San Diego County, California:** Leads with **195.00 applicants per job**, indicating a highly competitive market.
- **Scotts Valley, California:** Follows with **151.00 applicants per job**, showing significant interest within the state.
- **Cambridge, Ontario, Canada:** Has **144.00 applicants per job**, reflecting a strong demand in Canada.
- **Marnes-la-Coquette, Île-de-France, France:** Shows **143.00 applicants per job**, highlighting a competitive European market.
- **Sevenoaks, England, United Kingdom:** Presents **140.00 applicants per job**, indicating high competition in the UK.
- **La Défense, Île-de-France, France:** With **130.33 applicants per job**, it shows a steady interest in France.
- **Bedford, Massachusetts:** Offers **130.00 applicants per job**, reflecting a competitive market in the USA.
- **East Windsor, New Jersey:** Also has **130.00 applicants per job**, indicating a strong demand in New Jersey.
- **Stanford, California:** Shows **125.17 applicants per job**, highlighting significant interest in California.
- **Kitchener, Ontario, Canada:** Has **125.00 applicants per job**, reflecting a competitive market in Canada.

Conclusion:

The data reveals a highly competitive global job market for bioinformatics, particularly concentrated in California. For professionals seeking opportunities, understanding these regional dynamics is crucial for strategic career planning. Organizations looking to attract top talent should focus on these hotspots when designing recruitment strategies. This strategic approach can help stakeholders navigate the global bioinformatics job landscape effectively.

2.1.3 Global Bioinformatics Job Landscape: Strategic Insights for Workforce Allocation

Key Insights:

- **United States of America:** Leads significantly with **1715 job postings**, indicating a robust market and high demand for bioinformatics skills.
- **United Kingdom:** Second highest with **469 job postings**, suggesting a strong but smaller market compared to the USA.
- **Germany:** Offers **269 job postings**, showing a growing market in Europe.
- **France:** Has **169 job postings**, reflecting moderate opportunities.
- **Japan:** Presents **133 job postings**, indicating a niche but stable market.
- **Netherlands:** With **89 job postings**, it shows emerging opportunities.
- **Canada:** Offers **25 job postings**, highlighting potential growth areas.
- **Nigeria:** Has **3 job postings**, suggesting an emerging market with room for development.
- **Ghana:** The lowest with **2 job postings**, indicating a nascent market.

Conclusion:

The data highlights a concentration of bioinformatics job opportunities in the USA and UK, making these countries key hubs for talent in this field. For professionals seeking employment or companies looking to invest in talent acquisition, prioritizing these markets could be advantageous. Conversely, countries with lower job densities, such as Nigeria and Ghana, may benefit from targeted educational programs and incentives to cultivate local expertise and stimulate market growth. This strategic approach can help stakeholders navigate the global bioinformatics job landscape effectively.

2.1.4 Job Market Density: Number of Bioinformatics Job Postings by City

Key Insights:

- **London, England** leads with the highest job density for bioinformatics, boasting **163 job postings**.
- **Cambridge, Massachusetts** follows closely with **162 postings**, indicating a strong bioinformatics sector in the **United States**.
- **Chicago, Illinois** ranks third with **145 postings**, showing a significant drop from the top two cities.
- **Tokyo, Japan** is the only **non-Western city** in the top ten, with **108 job postings**, highlighting its emerging significance in the global bioinformatics landscape.
- **Boston, Massachusetts** has **117 postings**, further emphasizing the concentration of opportunities in select top-tier cities.
- **European cities** like **Oxford and Paris** show competitive numbers with **86 and 90 job** postings respectively, suggesting Europe's growing investment in bioinformatics sectors.
- **Philadelphia, Pennsylvania** and **Atlanta, Georgia** also feature prominently with **108 and 94 job postings** respectively.
- **San Diego, California** rounds out the list with **81 job postings**, indicating a diverse spread of opportunities across the **United States**.

Conclusion:

The chart highlights key urban centers as pivotal hubs for bioinformatics careers, with London and Cambridge leading. These cities offer robust opportunities, making them strategic locations for career development and business expansion.

2.2 Salary and Competitiveness

2.2.1 Global Bioinformatics Salaries: A Comparative Analysis

Country	Average Salary (USD)
France	263,635.71
United States of America	155,115.04
Germany	121,000.00
United Kingdom	60,738.90
Canada	35,040.00
Ghana	Not Available
Japan	Not Available
Netherlands	Not Available
Nigeria	Not Available

Key Insights:

- **France** offers the highest average salary for bioinformatics professionals at **\$263,635.71** per year.
- The **United States** follows with an average salary of **\$155,115.04**.
- **Germany** ranks third with an average salary of **\$121,000.00**.
- The **United Kingdom** and **Canada** have significantly lower average salaries at **\$60,738.90** and **\$35,040.00**, respectively.
- Salary data for **Ghana, Japan, Netherlands, and Nigeria** is not available, indicating a potential gap in data collection or reporting.

Conclusion:

The data highlights a significant disparity in bioinformatics salaries across different countries, with France leading the way. However, the absence of salary information for several countries and the varying proportion of job applications, particularly in the USA, suggest that these figures may not fully represent the best job offers globally. This analysis underscores the need for more comprehensive data to better understand the global landscape of bioinformatics salaries.

Industry and Sector Analysis

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The global bioinformatics market size generated \$8,614.29 million in 2019, and is projected to reach \$24,731.61 million by 2027, growing at a CAGR of 13.4% from 2020 to 2027.

Allied Market Research
A well-regarded market research provider.

3.1 Industry Diversity

3.1.1 Bioinformatics Boom: Unveiling Recruitment Trends in Key Industries

Key Insights:

- **Biotechnology Research** leads significantly with **511 postings**, indicating a high demand for bioinformatics expertise within this field.
- **Higher Education** follows as the second-highest recruiter with **263 postings**, suggesting a strong academic interest and investment in bioinformatics talent.
- **Pharmaceutical Manufacturing** and **Staffing and Recruiting** are also key players, with **235** and **224 postings** respectively, showing their recognition of bioinformatics as an essential asset.
- **Technology, Information and Internet** (170), **Hospitals and Health Care** (163), **Research Services** (102), **IT Services & IT Consulting** (99), **Science & Technology Consulting** (90), **Business Consulting and Services** (81) all showcase substantial recruitment activity, reflecting the widespread integration of bioinformatics across diverse sectors.

Conclusion:

The data underscores a robust job market for bioinformatics professionals across various industries. With Biotechnology Research at the forefront, it is evident that there is an urgent need for skilled individuals who can bridge biology and data science. This trend presents an opportunity for professionals to leverage their expertise in bioinformatics to advance their careers in multiple sectors. It also signals to educational institutions the importance of equipping students with skills relevant to these growing demands.

3.2 Recruitment Trends

3.2.1 Dominance of Full-time Positions in Bioinformatics

Key Insights:

- **Full-time positions** dominate the bioinformatics industry with **2570 job postings**, indicating a strong preference for long-term employment.
- **Contract positions** are the second most common, but significantly lower at **157 postings**.
- **Part-time roles** have **71 postings**, showing limited availability.
- **Internship opportunities** are scarce, with only **25 postings**.
- **Other employment types** account for **29 postings**, indicating niche opportunities.
- **Temporary positions** are the least available, with just **14 postings**.

Conclusion: The data highlights a clear preference for full-time employment in the bioinformatics sector, suggesting stability and a high demand for long-term commitment. Professionals seeking to enter or grow in this field should prioritize full-time opportunities. Contract positions offer an alternative for those seeking flexibility. The limited availability of internships and temporary roles suggests these may not be reliable entry points into the industry.

Job Characteristics and Skills

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Bioinformatics combines science, mathematics, computer science and data analysis to study and solve complex biological problems.

Indeed
A free job search engine with millions
of listings across all industries.

4.1 Popular Job Titles

4.1.1 Identifying the Most Popular Job Titles in Bioinformatics Based on Applicant Data

Key Insights:

- **Scientist** is the most sought-after title with **1,204 applicants**, leading the bioinformatics job market.
- **Bioinformatics Scientist** follows with **1,019 applications**, showing strong interest in specialized roles.
- **Associate Research Scientist** attracted **872 applicants**, reflecting demand for mid-level research positions.
- **Online Biology Tutor - Part Time** received **810 applicants**, highlighting interest in teaching, even part-time.
- **Bioinformatician (701)** and **Software Engineer (694)** show demand for analytical and computational skills.
- **Scientist Molecular Diagnostics Liquid Biopsy (666)**, **Clinical Scientist (555)**, and **Associate Scientist (535)** also attracted steady interest.
- **Bioinformatician/Research Data Analyst** had **519 applicants**, indicating consistent demand across varied roles.

Conclusion:

The bioinformatics market shows strong demand for both research and computational roles, with Scientist and Bioinformatics Scientist leading in popularity. This trend highlights the need for specialized expertise, guiding future hiring strategies.

4.2 Skills Demand

4.2.1 Driving Bioinformatics Growth: Spotlight on Analytical Tools, AI, and Sequencing Technologies

Category	Tool/Term/Platform	Count
Demand for Analytical Tools	R	2874
	Excel	1667
	Python	641
	SQL	159
	Bash	51
	Power BI	23
Demand for Other Technologies	Git	383
	Conda	92
	Docker	56
	Github	51
	Javascript	27
	REST API	2
	Java	0
	C++	0
Demand for Cloud Platforms	GCP	161
	AWS	142
	Azure	55

Category	Tool/Term/Platform	Count
Demand for Sequencing Technologies	WGS	33
	Epigenetics	26
	RNA-seq	0
	Bulk/Single Cell Sequencing	0
Demand for Novel Techniques	CRISPR	282
	Imaging	202
	Single Cell Sequencing	23
Demand for Artificial Intelligence	Perturb-Seq	0
	AI	2635
	Machine Learning	412
Demand for Databases	Deep Learning	97
	TCGA	20
	DepMap	6
	gnomAD	6
	ENCODE	17
	NCBI SRA	0

Key Insights:

- **Analytical Tools Dominate:** R leads the demand with **2,874** mentions, significantly outpacing Excel (**1,667**) and Python (**641**). Notably, SQL (**159**) and Bash (**51**) also appear essential, while Power BI shows minimal demand (**23**).
- **Emerging Technologies in Bioinformatics:** Git commands the highest demand among supplementary technologies at **383** mentions, followed by Conda (**92**) and Docker (**56**). Tools like Java and C++ show no demand, revealing a narrowing focus on modern platforms.
- **Cloud Platforms Adoption:** GCP tops cloud demand with **161** mentions, followed by AWS (**142**) and Azure (**55**). This highlights GCP as the go-to platform for bioinformatics infrastructure.
- **Sequencing Technology Demand is Growing:** Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) shows moderate demand with **33** mentions, while epigenetics follows closely at **26**. Notably, RNA-seq and Bulk/Single Cell Sequencing are yet to gain traction, each showing **0** mentions.
- **Novel Techniques Lead Innovation:** CRISPR continues to drive interest in cutting-edge technologies with **282** mentions, while Imaging stands strong at **202**. In contrast, Perturb-Seq is at **0** demand, suggesting it's still emerging in bioinformatics research.

- **AI and Machine Learning Reshape Bioinformatics:** Artificial Intelligence leads this category with **2,635** mentions, showing its increasing role in bioinformatics. Machine Learning follows at **412**, and Deep Learning at **97**, marking a growing reliance on AI-driven insights.
- **Limited Database Focus:** Among bioinformatics databases, TCGA leads with **20** mentions, followed by ENCODE (**17**). Other databases like DepMap and gnomAD both show low demand (**6**), while NCBI SRA registers no demand (**0**).

Conclusion:

The bioinformatics landscape is evolving, with an overwhelming demand for AI, advanced analytical tools like R, and modern cloud platforms, particularly GCP. Despite advancements in novel techniques like CRISPR, there's room for growth in sequencing technologies and database utilization.

4.3 Seniority Levels

4.3.1 Career Advancement Across Academic Levels in Bioinformatics

Key Insights:

- **Entry-Level Opportunities:**

- **Highest Demand:** Positions at the entry-level show significant preference for candidates with Bachelor's degrees, with **371** positions available compared to **128** for Doctorate and **316** for Masters. Internships also predominantly require Bachelor's degrees (**108**), highlighting early career opportunities for this group.

- **Mid-Senior Level Dominance:**

- **Experienced Talent:** The mid-senior level is the most abundant category, with **1,018** positions for Bachelor's holders, **292** for Doctorates, and **1,258** for Masters. This indicates a strong need for experienced professionals, particularly those with Master's degrees.

- **Director and Executive Roles:**

- **Director Level:** Directors show a more balanced distribution across degrees, with **218** positions for Bachelor's, **29** for Doctorates, and **102** for Masters. The relatively small number of Executive positions (**4**) further emphasizes the competitive nature of top-tier roles.

- **Undergraduate and Not Applicable:**

- **Undergraduate Degree:** Positions requiring an undergraduate degree are notably low across most levels, except for the entry-level (**31**) and internship (**0**). This suggests limited opportunities for those with only an undergraduate degree.

Conclusion:

The data reveals a clear preference for Bachelor's degrees at entry-level and internship positions, while mid-senior and director roles show a more significant representation of Master's and Doctorate holders. The scarcity of executive positions underscores the high competition at the top level. For professionals aiming for growth, advancing from entry-level to mid-senior roles with a Master's degree offers substantial opportunities, while those with Doctorates are well-positioned for specialized or directorial roles.

Qualifications and Employers

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The educational requirements for bioinformatics role typically involve a combination of formal education and practical experience in relevant areas, such as biology, computer science and mathematics.

Indeed
A free job search engine with millions
of listings across all industries.

5.1 Common Degrees/Educational Background

5.1.1 Optimizing Qualifications for Bioinformatics Careers

Key Insights:

- **High Demand for Advanced Degrees:** Doctorate holders (**1,868 postings**) and Master's degree holders (**1,840 postings**) are overwhelmingly preferred for bioinformatics positions, suggesting that advanced education is a major driver for job opportunities in this field.
- **Moderate Interest in Post-Doctorate and Bachelor's:** While lower than Doctorate and Master's, Post-Doctorate (**656 postings**) and Bachelor's (**553 postings**) qualifications still represent significant interest, indicating the value of research and foundational degrees.
- **Minimal Opportunities for Undergraduates:** The chart highlights a stark contrast for undergraduates, with only **105 job postings**, signifying limited entry-level positions and an emphasis on higher education for bioinformatics roles.

Conclusion:

The bioinformatics job market clearly prioritizes advanced academic qualifications, with Doctorate and Master's degrees dominating job postings. This data underscores the importance of further education and research experience for those looking to pursue a career in bioinformatics.

5.2 Bioinformatics Employers

5.2.1 Top Companies Dominating Bioinformatics Job Postings: Varsity Tutors Leads the Pack

Key Insights:

- **Varsity Tutors, a Nerdy Company**, emerges as the frontrunner, with **73 job postings**, far exceeding other companies in the bioinformatics field.
- **myGwork - LGBTQ+ Business Community** follows closely, posting **60 job opportunities**, showcasing a strong focus on diversity and inclusion in hiring.
- **University of Pennsylvania** and **BioSpace** maintain competitive momentum with **59** and **56 postings** respectively, indicating academic and industry commitment to bioinformatics roles.
- **BioNTech SE**, known for its contributions to the biopharmaceutical space, posted **41 jobs**, emphasizing the growing intersection of bioinformatics and cutting-edge health solutions.
- **Emory University** and **Augusta University** each posted **33 jobs**, reflecting the growing need for bioinformatics professionals in academic research environments.
- **Bristol Myers Squibb** posted **31 roles**, underscoring the pharmaceutical sector's increasing reliance on bioinformatics for drug discovery and development.
- **Lifelancer** and **Thermo Fisher Scientific** posted **27** and **26** jobs respectively, signaling significant contributions from the life sciences and biotech industries.

Conclusion:

The bioinformatics job market is thriving, with **Varsity Tutors** standing out as the dominant employer. This insight highlights opportunities for bioinformatics professionals across a diverse range of sectors, from academic institutions to cutting-edge biopharmaceutical companies.

Appendix

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The capacity to blunder slightly is the real marvel of DNA. Without this special attribute, we would still be anaerobic bacteria and there would be no music.

Lewis Thomas
Author of *The Lives of a Cell: Notes of a Biology Watcher*

Glossary

- **Bioinformatics:** The application of computational techniques to the analysis and interpretation of biological data.
- **Job Density:** The number of job postings per location.
- **Applicant-to-Job Ratio:** The number of applicants per job posting.
- **Salary Competitiveness:** The relative attractiveness of salaries in different locations.
- **Industry Diversity:** The distribution of bioinformatics jobs across various industries.
- **Recruitment Trends:** The patterns of job postings and hiring in the bioinformatics field.
- **Skill Demand:** The demand for specific skills and technologies in bioinformatics.
- **Seniority Levels:** The different levels of experience and responsibility within bioinformatics roles.
- **Qualifications:** The educational requirements and certifications needed for bioinformatics positions.
- **Employers:** The companies and organizations that hire bioinformatics professionals.

Methodology

This report is based on a comprehensive analysis of job data from LinkedIn. The data was collected and analyzed using various data analysis techniques to identify key trends and patterns.

Specific methodologies used include:

- **Web scraping:** Extracting job data from LinkedIn.
- **Data cleaning and processing:** Preparing the data for analysis.
- **Statistical analysis:** Identifying trends and patterns in the data.
- **Visualization:** Creating charts and graphs to illustrate key findings.

The entire codebase for this analysis, including the dataset and scripts for data processing and visualization, can be found in our GitHub repository: [GitHub Repository Link](#).

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Endnotes

- **Source of job data:** LinkedIn
- **Data collection period:** March 30, 2024 - June 30, 2024
- **Data collection tools:** BeautifulSoup 4 (Python 3.8)
- **Data Analysis Methods:**
 - **Data Cleaning:** Normalization of academic qualifications and tools (e.g., converting "msc" to "Masters").
 - **Frequency Analysis:** Counting occurrences of qualifications, skills, and tools to identify their demand.
 - **Categorization:** Grouping qualifications and seniority levels.
 - **Visualization:** Bar plots created using matplotlib to visualize the demand for skills, tools, and technologies.
- **Limitations of the Study:**
 - **Data Representation:** The dataset might not represent the entire bioinformatics job market, leading to potential sampling bias.
 - **Normalization Challenges:** Inconsistent naming conventions across job postings could affect accuracy despite data cleaning.
 - **Missing Information:** Some job postings may lack complete data on qualifications or skills, skewing the results.
 - **Technological Bias:** The focus on specific tools and technologies could miss emerging or niche tools not covered in the dataset.

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